

The School Of The Gifted Session Plan (Remixable version)

This is the remixable version of the session plan presented at Mozfest 2019. The plan was designed for a 60-minute session and can be easily be modified for groups of all sizes.

This session was directed to raise awareness about Neurodiversities and was designed to help people identify their special skills and interests. It can easily be adapted to other subjects and populations if required.

The plan was created by session co-facilitators Natalia Norori and Isabella Sevilla and is licensed CC-BY 4.0. For inquiries please contact [Natalia](#) or [Isabella](#).

Session Goal

- Brainstorm ways to help neurodiverse individuals embrace what makes them different, and raise awareness on the positive qualities and perspectives they can bring to social development, communities, spaces, and events.
- Empower communities to promote safe spaces that uplift the participation of neurodiverse voices, helping them maximize their potential to be active change-makers.

Session Description for participants

We believe all participants at the festival have been gifted with the Mozfest-gene, which enhances special abilities unique to each person. The workshop invites Mozfesters to highlight their special abilities, shifting the focus from the negative and enhancing what makes them special. The new generation of gifted youngsters and adults (both neurodiverse and neurotypical, everyone is invited!) that attend the workshop will have the opportunity to build their own abilities trading cards, inspired in the x-men trading cards created by Marvel.

After making the cards, we will reflect on how institutions, communities, and events might create spaces that help maximize the potential of their members.

Those who are willing will have the opportunity to share their trading cards with others and contribute with recommendations of good practices to create inclusive spaces that uplift the voices of the next generation of gifted youngsters and adults.

participants will be encouraged to use their diverse skills to collaborate and create an interactive toolkit, inspired in the workshop dynamic, that highlights special qualities, and encourages communities to create safe, inclusive spaces that uplift neurodiverse voices in communities and events.

Session Plan

Before the session

- 1. Review the session plan and get feedback**
- 2. Get informed.** We have curated a list of articles that can help you understand the subject before you start planning your session:
 - [The Stanford Interest Group for Neurodiversity](#)
 - [Neurodiversity: What you need to know](#)
 - [The Myth of the Normal Brain](#)
 - [Insights from the BRAINHE project](#)
- 3. Make sure you have all the materials needed for the session. For our session we used:**
 - A projector (a laptop could also work)
 - A tablet or phone with adobe connect installed (optional)
 - Post-its
 - Markers, crayons and colored pencils
 - A3 paper
 - Scissors
 - Rulers
- 4. Get comfortable with the room you'll be running your session in.**
 - Have the materials ready before the participants arrive, this will ensure you don't spend your session time doing so.
 - For our session, we set up small tables with seats for 3-4 participants each and divided our materials to make sure all participants had everything they needed to create their trading cards.
 - Make sure the lighting in the room is friendly.
 - Make sure the room is accessible for session participants with special needs.

During the session

1. Introduce the session goals and ice-breaking activity (10 minutes)

- Introduce yourself (points if you transmit excitement while doing so, participants appreciate knowing they're talking to someone who cares about the subject).
- Know your audience. Try to be as inclusive as possible, make sure you have pen and paper for those not comfortable with verbal communication.
- Invite each participant to say (quickly, in one sentence) their name, pronouns and one thing that makes them different. We'll have pen and paper for those not comfortable with verbal language
- Briefly explain the dynamic of the session. Don't forget to state that we are going to base our session in the school of gifted youngsters and young adults from X-men

2. Discussion: Share your qualities (10 minutes) (optional)

- If participants are comfortable, we encourage you to invite them to break into small groups and share how their differences make them special, give more details about their accomplishment, and ways in which society and their organizations have helped them, highlight their qualities

3. Deepening: Make your own trading card (30 minutes)

- The core activity of the session is to inspire participants to display their qualities, special gifts, and abilities by making their own trading cards, inspired in trading card games popular during the 90s. We created our own personalized trading card templates for the session, you can show them as examples, or create your own!
 - Give a brief introduction to the trading card templates and invite participants to make their own. Encourage them to be creative and make changes to the templates as much as they want.
 - Make sure to have enough materials to allow participants to be creative. The materials suggested are listed above.
 - Encourage participants to write recommendations to communities and spaces to help them show their superpowers. Invite them to answer two questions:
 - How might we empower others and help them share their qualities?
 - What's the role of institutions, conferences, and spaces during this process?

- Once participants are done, they will be able to scan their power card and have it sent to their email. We encourage you to save copies of the scans with the participant's permission to share as feedback.

4. Synthesis (5 minutes)

- Summarise the session, review what participants achieved, and identify any next steps.
- Share the session notes and resources
- Make sure participants have a way to reach out to you in the future.

After the session

1. Sharing is caring

Share the session outcomes on your social media profile or with anyone who might be interested if you want!

2. Email the participants and ask for feedback

3. Let us know how it went!

- We would love to learn more about your session. Please contact Natalia or Isabella at natalianorori@gmail.com / isabellasevilla25@gmail.com to share your learnings.
- [Sign up as a contributor](#) to the Github repository and contribute your learnings in the [issues section](#).

We hope the information above helps you remix the session! If you have any questions or would like to chat, [contact us](#) and let us know.